

Experience in the exam preparation of CPALE on the candidates of selected schools within Cavite and nearby cities to enhance licensure performance

Khryzsteen Mari V. Ongogan*, Jorenz M. Undag, William T. Viray
Accountancy Department, School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of Asia,
Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
*Corresponding author

Abstract

The researchers aim to reflect on the perception of the respondents to what extent they perceive their experience in preparation for the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Exams (CPALE) in terms of their capacity to adapt to online review class and in terms of their capacity to attain effective online learning review. The research was conducted in different colleges and universities near Cavite through a descriptive survey. When it came to the profiles of the respondents, only gender (P -values=0.0009 & 0.0029) was found to be significant. On the other hand, age (P -values=0.6155 & 0.6070), year of graduation (P -values=0.5204 & 0.4893), and colleges/universities (P -values=0.9783 & 0.3439) were found to be insignificant in the perception of respondents for both capacities to adapt to online review and capacity to attain effective online learning review. Demographic profile is not a factor in the way the respondents perceive their experience in the exam preparation for CPALE during the pandemic. Most of them had the same positive and negative experiences. Online reviews affected the respondents' experience in their exam preparation as everything is new to them. About their available technology devices, respondents believed that using computers, laptops, and tablets gave them the most positive experience during online reviews, making online learning easier rather than using a mobile phone due to its small screen, while the compatibility and storage of their devices also affect their learning experience during an online review. Respondents perceived adapting to online review and attaining effective online learning at moderately high to high levels, respectively.

Keywords: Experience; Exam preparation; Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination; School; Licensure performance.

To cite this article:

Ongogan, K. M. V., Undag, J. M., & Viray, W. T. (2022). Experience in the exam preparation of CPALE on the candidates of selected schools within Cavite and nearby cities to enhance licensure performance. *SDCA Journal of Accountancy*, 3, 44-57.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has impacted the entire licensure examinations, resulting in delays and a shift to more technology-based examinations (Galvez, 2020). The Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC) had to cancel several licensure examinations for two years in the Philippines due to the underlying COVID-19 situation. These left students confused, anxious, and drained of the money and resources candidates would spend on board examination reviews (Sison, 2021). Also, the sudden shift to online learning with the use of computers and online review classes was an unforeseen situation for the candidates for board exams (Cabatbat, 2022). All of these require a stable internet connection and digitalized learning environment and resources, while students are found struggling with adapting to online classes, experiencing exam anxiety, and lack of hope (Schroeder, 2020).

The researchers decided to conduct this study to reflect on the experience faced by the candidates in their exam preparation during the pandemic, coupled with its deferment and sudden shift in the online

review setup. Exam preparation refers to a learning course, tutoring/review services, learning materials, or learning tools designed to improve students' performance on a standardized test. Students who prepare for the exams are more likely to pass the exams. Hence, the licensure examination involves preparation considering registering for refresher courses or reviewing schools.

Due to COVID-19, licensure examinations are being deferred, and students must adapt to online review classes as one of the viable ways for continuous learning and exam preparation. The effects of delay and continuous deferment of exams will expand and negatively affect the licensure performance of the students. In fact, Morgan (2015) revealed that the delay in taking Certified Public Accountant (CPA) exams has a significant negative relationship with exam pass rates because of memory fading, curriculum content changing, and work and family responsibilities increasing over time reducing available time for review. That is why students continue with their exam preparation during a pandemic regardless of its deferment and sudden shift in the online review setup, even if it is a possible problem for them. While some students find online review classes advantageous, others find it difficult to cope with online review classes, which will negatively affect the student's academic success and future careers.

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to determine the experience in exam preparation of Certified Public Accountant Licensure Exams (CPALE) by the candidates during the pandemic. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents?
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Year of graduation
 - 1.4 College/University
2. To what extent do the respondents determine their experience in exam preparation?
 - 2.1 Capacity to adapt to online review class
 - 2.1.1 Access to Internet connection
 - 2.1.2 Available technology device
 - 2.1.3 Technological literacy
 - 2.2 Capacity to attain effective online learning review
 - 2.2.1 Comfortable learning environment
 - 2.2.2 Sufficient learning resources
 - 2.2.3 Adequate support from family and friends
 - 2.2.4 Motivation to study
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondent as to their experience in exam preparation when grouped according to profile?
4. Based on the findings what are the necessary recommendations to enhance the CPA licensure examination performance?

Related Studies

CPALE is considered one of the most difficult board exams in the country (Ballado-Tan, 2015; Pattaguan, 2018). The board exam for Certified Public Accountants of the Philippines is recognized as a complex, challenging, and enduring professional exam that is equal in coverage and breadth of assessment of their own practice (Lianza, 2016). But earning the title requires a lot of preparation and perseverance to pass the tough board exam. Obtaining licensure is not easy; graduates who aim for licensure should enter review schools after graduation to prepare for their professional exams.

For those who graduated in 2020, six months of preparation before the board exams turned into one year and six months and longer. The pandemic restrictions have changed the way these graduates typically study. They now need to take online classes through review centers, discuss difficult concepts with friends through social messaging applications, and practice studying on their laptops (Barrot et al., 2021). While most students believe that accounting subjects can never be taught effectively online because of their difficulty and complexity (Niemojko & Tolan, 2020). Candidates for the CPA licensure exam will likely have difficulty passing the exam if they do not study well in the initial stages. This situation will inspire the academia to address best practices and research more effective teaching techniques to improve education.

The paradigm shifts in the way educators conduct review centers through various online platforms can be an entirely different experience for candidates and educators, which they must adapt to with no other alternatives available. However, student readiness must be measured and supported accordingly to adapt to the new changes. Learners with a fixed mindset have difficulty adapting and adjusting, while learners with a growth mindset adapt quickly to new learning environments (Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021). Meanwhile, the impact of online learning is a pedagogical method of concern for universities that promises to improve student achievement through improved computer/internet literacy, self-directed learning, and motivation to learn (Allam et al., 2020). Various disciplines and age groups necessitate various ways of online learning (Doucet et al., 2020). On the other hand, age has always been the borderline of online education and can affect online students' success (Glazier et al., 2019). Young students have the opposite view and are devoted to face-to-face lessons. Others find the recorded lecture video slow and multitasking with other activities. Therefore, students' perception of online learning depends on age, because older students usually prefer online learning, and younger students often prefer face-to-face events. In contrast, older students may suffer from technical or family needs and may have poor performance in online classes, or their experience and motives could make them more successful (Knestrick et al., 2016; Wladis et al., 2015). Therefore, age has become a factor to the research.

Gender has a significant role in adapting online education (Bisht et al., 2022). Males can employ more learning techniques and have greater technical skills than females in online learning contexts (Alghamdi et al., 2020). As learning switches to online, students accustomed to traditional learning or face-to-face interactions may confront obstacles. Students are observed to be dealing with correct adaptation to instructional trends, technological concerns such as poor literacy in computer and smartphone handling, poor internet signaling that disrupts their online connectivity, and unbalanced time management (Allam et al., 2020). Cabatbat (2022) said that graduates from 2020 had unforeseen adjustments in online learning review to prepare for their licensure exams.

One of the major causes contributing to the issues faced by candidates in online review classes is their ability to adapt to technology, which makes it difficult for them to perform successfully. According to Wilson (2018), one of the current issues in the educational system is internet connectivity. Offering a quick and efficient service is essential, and so the ideal approach to performing technology-based teaching is to have a stable internet connection. There are still some regions with inadequate internet access, as some are in blackspot zones, and many students do not have access to their smartphones or televisions at home and have poor internet connections.

Some of the problems that slowed the adaptation of technology in schools were the digital divide and students' lack of digital literacy to use new technologies in the classroom (Dashtestani and Hojatpanah, 2022). Students will be more ready to learn how to utilize such technologies in learning if they are made more accessible to them. Their levels of digital literacy on new platforms will improve if they are given the opportunity to be educated. In fact, for the first time, online platforms such as Google Classroom, Zoom, virtual learning environments, social media, and other group forums such as Telegram, Messenger, WhatsApp, and WeChat are studied for teaching and learning.

With the right technology, online reviews can be beneficial in various ways, as they can provide much content, interactions, flexibility, and reinforcement (Surkhali & Garbuja, 2020). Because a typical issue among students' responses to this form of learning is the drawbacks of mobile devices, such as the

small screen, restricted input possibilities, and poor processing capacity, mobile devices are not always seen as beneficial instruments for students' learning (Ting et al., 2020).

Furthermore, a rising number of students are smartphone-dependent, relying entirely on smartphones for Internet access rather than more expensive devices such as laptops and tablets (Anderson & Horrigan, 2016). According to surveys, two-thirds of students use mobile devices for learning. They believe that technology may assist them in achieving learning objectives and better prepare them for a technologically dependent workforce (Chen et al., 2015).

The researchers addressed the gaps in the candidates' experience in preparation of the CPALE and its barriers to technology integration. However, one limitation of literature is a lack of detail about how teaching and learning practices were used to select and integrate technology into learning. Thus, it is unclear how teaching and learning practices may have influenced student performance levels in their online reviews.

Methodology

Research Design

To fulfill the objectives of the study, a quantitative design was held. This method involves collecting data, objective measurements, and providing statistical and mathematical analysis of data through descriptive research design (survey design). The questionnaire consists of 35 items wherein the experiences in exam preparation of the candidates on CPALE during the pandemic are measured by two variables composed of capacity to adapt to an online review class and capacity to attain effective online learning review. To measure the capacity of the candidates to adapt to the online review class, it includes fifteen questions (n=15) consisting of three sub-variables: access to internet connection (n=5), available electronic device (n=5), and technological literacy (n=5). Items linked under this variable determine the candidates' ability to use online resources and evaluate the availability of devices used for online review. Under the capacity of the candidates to attain effective online learning review, it has included twenty questions (n=20) consisting of four sub-variables: comfortable learning environment (n=5), sufficient learning resources (n=5), adequate support from family and friends (n=5), and motivation to study (n=5). The items related to this variable evaluate the capacity of the candidates to adjust to the new set of online learning, the candidates' capability to acquire modules, test banks and reviewers, and candidates' state in terms of financial and moral support from the family and friends and the candidates' capability to go beyond his/her comfort zone, especially during this pandemic.

Population Sample

The target population of this study includes BSA graduates of different colleges and universities in the school year of 2020-2021, and the accessible population is within seven selected schools in Cavite and nearby cities, since these are the graduates beyond the researchers' reach. The sample for the study consisted of 75 BSA graduates of different colleges and universities near Cavite, assumed to be candidates for CPA licensure exams, compared to 202 graduates in the initial sample.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire designed by the researchers was used in the study. The content of the instrument has two parts. The first part is the respondents' profiles, and the second part consists of the questions that determine the experiences in exam preparation on CPALE during pandemic. The research instrument was administered directly to the chosen sample for the study. A Google form was e-mailed to

different BSA graduates who would take the CPA licensure examination within the areas near Cavite. The researchers ascertained that the respondents had access to the form on mobiles or desktops using their e-mails. The researchers reached out to different students, friends, and schools and asked their permission to be part of the study and sent a copy of the questionnaires.

Statistical Treatment

The data collected from the questionnaires responded by the BSA graduates were statistically analyzed. Likert scale and one-way ANOVA were used to analyze the data quantitatively. The psychometric response scale is mainly used in questionnaire surveys to obtain participants' preferences or agreement with one or a group of statements. Respondents were asked to indicate their degree of agreement with a given statement on an ordinal scale. The researchers used one-way ANOVA to determine whether the differences between group means are statistically significant.

Table 1. Likert scale

Range (SQ)	Range (Likert Scale)	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
4	3.41-4.20	Agree (A)
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree (DA)
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree (SDA)

The researchers used a 5-point scale in the questionnaires ranging from Strongly Disagree on one end to Strongly Agree on the other, with Moderately Agree in the middle. It is to identify the degree of agreement of every BSA graduate regarding their different experiences encountered in exam preparation during deferment of CPALE.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Demographic profile of respondents (n=75)

Category	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)	Over 30	1	1.3
	26 – 30	8	10.7
	21 – 25	8	10.7
	Below 21	58	77.3
Gender	Male	28	37.3
	Female	47	62.7
Year of Graduation	2020	51	68.0
	2021	24	32.0
School	Cavite State University – Indang Campus	10	13.3
	De La Salle University – Dasmariñas	11	14.7
	Dr. Filemon C. Aguilar Memorial College of Las Piñas	10	13.3
	St. Dominic College of Asia	11	14.7
	University of Perpetual Help – GMA Campus	8	10.7
	University of Perpetual Help Dalta – Las Piñas	13	17.3
	University of Perpetual Help Dalta – Molino Campus	12	16.0

Table 2 reflects the demographic profile of respondents. As reflected in the table, in terms of age, 77.3% (58 respondents) are below 21 years old, 10.7% (8 respondents) are ages 21 to 25 years old, 10.7% (8 respondents) are ages 26 to 30 years old, and only 1.3% (1 respondent) ages over 30 years old. In general, majority of respondents in this study are below 21 years old.

In terms of gender, 62.70% (47 respondents) are females, while 37.30% (28 respondents) are males. In general, most of the respondents in this study are females. In terms of year of graduation, 68% (51 respondents) graduated last 2020, while 32% (24 respondents) graduated last 2021. In terms of college/university, 17.30% (13 respondents) came from UPHSD – Las Piñas, 16.00% (12 respondents) came from UPHSD – Molino Campus, 14.70% (11 respondents) came from DLSU – Dasmariñas, 14.70% (11 respondents) came from SDCA, 13.30% (10 respondents) came from CvSU – Indang Campus, 13.30% (10 respondents) came from DFCAM College of Las Piñas, and only 10.70% (8 respondent) came from UPH – GMA. In general, most respondents in this study are from UPHSD – Las Piñas.

Table 3. Extent of Respondents' Experience in Exam Preparation for CPALE in Terms of Capacity to Adapt to Online Review Class

Component	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Access to Internet Connection	3.74	Agree	1
Available Technology Device	3.61	Agree	2
Technological Literacy	3.41	Agree	3
Weighted Mean	3.59	Agree	

Table 3 shows the respondents' perception of their experience in the capacity to adapt to online review classes during their exam preparation for CPALE. It is viewed at a high level and has a weighted mean of 3.59. From the three sub-variables, access to internet connection is perceived to be with the highest rating of 3.74, followed by available technology devices with 3.61, and technological literacy with the lowest rating of 3.42.

Table 4. Extent of Experience in Exam Preparation of Respondents in Terms of Access to Internet Connection

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can listen to the instructor clearly because I have my own Wi-Fi connection for my online review.	3.75	Agree	2
2. I have stable Internet connection for downloading videos/files for my uninterrupted online review.	3.71	Agree	3
3. Using pocket Wi-Fi during online discussions is not stable for my online review.	3.59	Agree	5
4. Using mobile data when taking exams online makes learning inconvenient.	3.60	Agree	4
5. Having slow internet connection interrupts my online review.	4.08	Agree	1
Weighted Mean	3.74	Agree	

Table 4 manifests the extent of experience in exam preparation of respondents in terms of capacity to adapt to online review classes to access internet connection. As manifested in the table, the statement "having a slow internet connection interrupts my online review" has the highest rating with a weighted mean of 4.08 or verbally interpreted as agree. In summary, students agreed that access to an internet connection is one way to adapt to online review classes in preparation for the examination, with a general weighted mean of 3.75.

Table 5 manifests the extent of experience in exam preparation of respondents in terms of capacity to adapt to online review class as to available technology devices in an online review class. Students agreed in using a computer for their online review that makes it easier to study with the highest rating of 4.00, or verbally interpreted as agree. This implies students getting the most positive experience during an online review when using this kind of gadget, compared to using a mobile phone with a mean of 3.77. In summary, they agreed that the availability of the technological device is one way to adapt to online review classes in preparation for the examination, with a general weighted mean of 3.61.

Table 5. Extent of Experience in Exam Preparation of Respondents in Terms of Available Technology Device

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Using computer for my online review makes it easier to study (e.g., personal computer, laptop, and tablet)	4.00	Agree	1
2. Using mobile phone for my online review makes it difficult to study because the screen is too small.	3.77	Agree	2
3. My device is compatible with the platforms used for my online review.	3.61	Agree	3
4. My device has a large storage device for downloadable files during online review.	3.29	Moderately Agree	5
5. My device hangs/lags sometimes during my online review.	3.37	Moderately Agree	4
Weighted Mean	3.61	Agree	

Table 6. Extent of Experience in Exam Preparation of Respondents in Terms of Technological Literacy

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I have limited skill in using technology during my online review.	3.41	Agree	3
2. I have limited knowledge of new digital learning platforms used in my online review.	3.24	Moderately Agree	5
3. I am having a hard time using digital devices during my online review.	3.64	Agree	1
4. I cannot fully understand how to use the applications needed for my online review.	3.47	Agree	2
5. I have limited understanding in accessing online information and other resource database.	3.28	Moderately Agree	4
Weighted Mean	3.41	Agree	

Table 6 shows the extent of experience in exam preparation of respondents in terms of capacity to adapt online review class to technological literacy on online review class. They agreed that they are having a hard time using a digital device with the highest rating of 3.64. As a result, respondents mostly have negative experiences with technological literacy and agreed that adapting to online review classes in preparation for the examination is essential, with a general weighted mean of 3.41.

Table 7. Extent of Respondents' Experience in Exam Preparation of CPALE in Terms of Capacity to Attain Effective Online Learning Review

Component	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Comfortable learning environment	3.30	Moderately Agree	3
Sufficient learning resources	3.25	Moderately Agree	4
Adequate support from family and friends	3.64	Agree	1
Motivation to study	3.32	Moderately Agree	2
Weighted Mean	3.38	Moderately Agree	

Table 7 shows the respondents' perception of their experience in the capacity to attain effective online learning review during their exam preparation for CPALE. It is viewed with a weighted mean of 3.38. From the four sub-variables, adequate support from family and friends is perceived with the highest means of 3.64, followed by motivation to study with a mean of 3.32, comfortable learning environment with a mean of 3.30, and sufficient learning resources with the lowest mean of 3.25.

Table 8. Extent of Experience in Exam Preparation of Respondents in Terms of Comfortable Learning Environment

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I cannot focus on home during my online review due to lot of distractions (e.g. noise, children, television).	3.67	Agree	1
2. I have study area at home where I can focus on my online review.	3.31	Moderately Agree	3
3. I enjoy online review discussions because I can record and get back to it whenever I want to.	3.60	Agree	2
4. I can freely communicate with my Instructor during my review when I have questions.	2.99	Moderately Agree	4
5. I can engage in group study/discussions with my fellow candidates during online review.	2.92	Moderately Agree	5
Weighted Mean	3.30	Moderately Agree	

Table 8 shows the extent of respondents' experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to attain effective online learning review as to have a comfortable learning environment in an online review class. As manifested in the table, having no focus at home during online review due to distractions is perceived as the highest mean of 3.67, contrary to those who enjoy online discussions with a study area with a mean of 3.60. Nonetheless, these two indicators are verbally interpreted as agree. Thus, students agreed that a comfortable learning environment is one way to attain an effective online learning review in preparation for the examination, with a general weighted mean of 3.38.

Table 9. Extent of Experience in Exam Preparation of Respondents in Terms of Sufficient Learning Resources

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I have more offline review materials than online (e.g., books, handouts, notes)	3.19	Moderately Agree	3
2. I have complete reference books about the course syllabus of CPALE.	3.12	Moderately Agree	4
3. I have access to online review materials (e.g., recorded discussions, e-books and journals, online reviewers).	3.48	Agree	1
4. I have enough activity questions to test my analytical thinking (e.g., test banks, past exam papers, practical accounting).	3.40	Moderately Agree	2
5. I have opportunity to attend tutorials/webinars (either face-to-face or online).	3.08	Moderately Agree	5
Weighted Mean	3.25	Moderately Agree	

Table 9 shows the extent of respondents' experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to attain effective online learning review as to their sufficient learning resources. As manifested in the table, they have access to online review materials, which is perceived with the highest mean of 3.48 or verbally interpreted as agree. Therefore, students agreed that having sufficient learning resources is one way to attain an effective online learning review in preparation for the examination, with a general weighted mean of 3.25.

Table 10 shows the extent of respondents' experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to attain effective online learning review as to adequate support from family and friends. As manifested in the table, they were satisfied with their family support, which is perceived as having the highest rating of 3.77. All these five indicators are verbally interpreted as agree. Thus, they agreed that having adequate support from family and friends is one way to attain effective online learning review in preparation for the examination, with a general weighted mean of 3.64.

Table 10. Extent of Experience in Exam Preparation of Respondents in Terms of Adequate Support from Family and Friends

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. My family gives me encouragement during my online review.	3.64	Agree	3
2. My friends provide support through my goals that need to be accomplished.	3.64	Agree	2
3. My family supports all expenses needed for my online review.	3.56	Agree	5
4. My friends help me to cope with stress during my online review.	3.60	Agree	4
5. I am satisfied with my family support that keeps me motivated to review online.	3.77	Agree	1
Weighted Mean	3.64	Agree	

Table 11. Extent of Experience in Exam Preparation of Respondents in Terms of Motivation to Study

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I am motivated to review even its online during the delay with CPALE.	3.49	Agree	2
2. Even when online learning is hard, I keep working until I finish.	3.72	Agree	1
3. I am not motivated during online review.	2.89	Moderately Agree	5
4. I became complacent on my online review during the pandemic.	3.40	Moderately Agree	3
5. I cannot review online effectively due to the challenge in learning given by the pandemic.	3.08	Moderately Agree	4
Weighted Mean	3.32	Moderately Agree	

Table 11 shows the extent of respondents' experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to attain effective online learning review as to motivation to study. As manifested in the table, respondents believe that even though online learning is difficult, they work hard until they finish which perceived with the highest mean of 3.72, followed by them being motivated even if it is online with a mean of 3.49 or verbally interpreted as agree. While other respective statements with means of 3.40, 3.08, and 2.89 are all verbally interpreted as moderately agree.

Table 12. Significant difference on the perception of the respondent as to their experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to adapt to online review class

Variables	Source of Variation	DF	SS	MS	F-stat	P-value	Decision
Age	Between Groups	3	1.0371	0.3457	0.6025	0.6155	Accept
	Within Groups	71	40.7379	0.5738			
	Total	74	41.7751				
Gender	Between Groups	1	5.8695	5.8695	11.9335	0.0009	Accept
	Within Groups	73	35.9055	0.4919			
	Total	74	41.7751				
Year of Graduation	Between Groups	1	0.2373	0.2373	0.4171	0.5204	Accept
	Within Groups	73	41.5377	0.5690			
	Total	74	41.7751				
Colleges / Universities	Between Groups	6	0.6928	0.1155	0.1911	0.9783	Accept
	Within Groups	68	41.0823	0.6042			
	Total	74	41.7751				

Table 12 shows the significant difference in the perception of respondents as regards their experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to adapt to online review class. There is a significant difference in the perception of the respondents in terms of capacity to adapt to online review class when respondents are grouped according to gender (P-value=0.0009). The resulting p-values are less than the significant level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected. When grouped according to age (P-value=0.6155), year graduated (P-value=0.5204), and colleges/universities (P-value=0.9783), there is no significant difference in the respondents' perceptions. The resulting p-value is greater than the significant level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 13. Significant difference on the perception of the respondent as to their experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to attain effective online learning review

Variables	Source of Variation	DF	SS	MS	F-stat	P-value	Decision
Age	Between Groups	3	1.0729	0.3576	0.6159	0.6070	Accept
	Within Groups	71	41.2274	0.5807			
	Total	74	42.3002				
Gender	Between Groups	1	4.8405	4.8405	9.5127	0.0029	Accept
	Within Groups	73	37.1457	0.5088			
	Total	74	41.9862				
Year of Graduation	Between Groups	1	0.2759	0.2759	0.4829	0.4893	Accept
	Within Groups	73	41.7103	0.5714			
	Total	74	41.9862				
Colleges / Universities	Between Groups	6	3.8653	0.6442	1.1492	0.3439	Accept
	Within Groups	68	38.1209	0.5606			
	Total	74	41.9862				

Table 13 shows the significant difference in the perception of respondents in terms of capacity to attain effective online learning review. The test of significance on respondents' perception of their experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to attain effective online learning review when grouped according to gender (P-value=0.0029) have lower results than the significant level. These indicate a significant difference exists, and the null hypothesis should be rejected. The test of significance on respondents' perception of their experience in exam preparation in terms of capacity to attain effective online learning review when grouped according to age (P-value=0.6070), year graduated (P-value=0.4893), and colleges/universities (P-value=0.3439) have p-values higher than the significant level indicating that there is no significant difference. Therefore, the null hypothesis should be accepted.

Discussion

The research population were BSA graduates of AY 2019-2021 who experienced online review classes due to the COVID-19 pandemic during their exam preparation for CPALE. It was obtained in colleges and universities in Cavite and nearby cities. Younger students prefer face-to-face sessions, while older students prefer online courses (Simonds & Brock, 2014), but in this study, researchers found that when respondents are grouped according to age, their perception about their experiences in exam preparation for CPALE during a pandemic does not have a significant difference.

When respondents were grouped by gender, this study revealed that there is a significant difference in their perceptions about their experiences in preparation for the CPALE in terms of capacity to adapt to online review class and to attain effective online learning review. This confirms the study made by Richardson and Woodley (2003) which found that online female learners are more perseverant and engaged than men, but males have more stable favorable attitudes regarding online learning (Nistor, 2013).

The year of graduation of the students is relevant to this research study, because it reflects the delay of the candidate in taking the CPA licensure examination. This result found that when respondents are

grouped according to their year of graduation, there is no significant difference in their perception of their experiences in preparation for CPALE. Meanwhile, in schools and universities, the study found no significant difference in the perception of the graduates regarding their experiences in preparation for CPALE during the pandemic.

Ting et al. (2020) stated that because a typical issue among students' responses to this form of learning is the drawbacks of mobile devices, such as the small screen, restricted input possibilities, and poor processing capacity, mobile devices are not always seen as useful instruments. Kapasia et al. (2020) studied how lockdown affects students' learning performance, which caused considerable disruptions in students' learning.

Numerous studies have shown that having someone to talk to can help you get through difficult circumstances. Someone could be that person for a pending board exam taker's family and friends. Adequate support within the family can operate as a stress buffer (Mariani et al., 2020), and the same can be true for friends (Adams et al., 2011). This study showed that the most positive experience of the candidates in attaining effective online learning review is getting support from their family and friends. According to Oakley and Pegrum (2015), with increased interaction and collaboration on online platforms, professors and students feel motivated and confident to take up the challenge of virtual teaching. In addition, lack of study space and lack of access to adequate online course materials hinder online learning (Abel, 2020).

Conclusion

This study is made to reflect on the experience in exam preparation during the pandemic encountered by Bachelor of Science in Accountancy candidates for the CPA licensure examination at selected colleges and universities in Cavite and nearby cities. The researchers found that access to an internet connection greatly affects how positive or negative their experience will be in their online review class, obtaining the highest means. Thus, students found it relatively difficult because everything was new to them, and they had to conform to the demands of the new ways of learning.

The researchers found that experiencing a slow internet connection strongly interrupts their online review while having their Wi-Fi and stable internet connection helps them to learn effectively from their instructors and download files and documents that they need for their review, giving them a positive experience. On the other hand, those who use prepaid internet and mobile data perceive learning as inconvenient and unstable, which is a negative experience for them. Though researchers have concluded that students may have internet connections in their homes, not everyone has access to a stable internet connection speed.

Respondents believe that using available technology devices such as computers, laptops, and tablets gave them the most positive experience during online reviews because it makes online learning easier than using a mobile phone due to its small screen, while the compatibility and storage of their devices also affect their learning experience. It makes learning difficult for some people because not everyone has the same devices to take advantage of their easy and ongoing online review class.

Respondents show that they experienced having limited knowledge and skills using digital devices as they newly adapted to the sudden shift of online review classes. Results showed that technological literacy obtained the most negative experience perceived by the respondents. Therefore, schools should provide their students with a tutorial or seminar on the digital learning platform. Researchers found that adequate support from their family and friends has given them the most positive experience in their preparation for CPALE.

In the sub-variable comfortable learning environment, most of the respondents have negative experiences of learning at home during online review classes due to a lot of distractions; they cannot freely communicate with the instructor and cannot engage in group discussions during online review, making

students' attention more divided while they are at home. In traditional face-to-face classes, they can devote their full attention to their academics and engage in class.

Regarding sufficient learning resources, the researchers found that respondents have more access to online review materials rather than offline review materials like books and handouts, concluding that most students depend on their learning resources on their digital devices. Therefore, digital devices help access and understand their materials during their online review class. Most of the respondents are satisfied with their families and friends' support and encouragement, helping them to cope with stress, and keeping them motivated, implying that social connection can boost student interest and motivation, as well as help them perform better. In the sub-variable motivation to study, respondents experienced becoming more motivated despite the challenges posed in the online reviews which caused delays in CPALE. Therefore, despite these challenges, their goal to become a CPA is enough for students to motivate them.

Regarding the significant difference in the perception of respondents in their experience in exam preparation, the capacity to adapt to online review class and to attain effective online learning review were found to be significant in terms of gender. Therefore, students' coping methods with online review classes as adopting the new normal vary with their gender. While other variables have no significant difference between the two sub-variables, students' approach to adapting to online review classes and attaining effective online learning review does not vary with their age bracket, how long they have graduated, and the schools where they belong.

Recommendations

Recommendations were made that may help future candidates to make online review classes manageable for everyone and help them towards better licensure performance. It is easier to adjust to an online review class if he or she has a steady internet connection, which is a primary concern for every candidate who prepares for their CPA exam. Most of the respondents believed that to have a better internet connection during online review discussions, the internet provider must improve their service. They also suggested that providing students with a free Wi-Fi connection would help them adjust to the online review setup.

The researchers also found that some respondents do not have enough available devices. They recommend that schools provide financial aid that can help those in need of digital resources. Devices with high specifications and large storage capacity are highly needed during an online review. Most of the respondents agreed that students should consider having their own study room or own space to focus on while learning is still done at home. They believe that distractions hinder them from completing their work and that online learning is only effective for those who have a good home environment.

In addition, respondents advised interactive online discussions and shared interactions for a more quality learning experience. Furthermore, they also believed that teachers should be encouraging and open to students to create a healthy learning environment online. About having sufficient learning resources, most students suggest that they still prefer offline materials to strengthen their fundamental concepts, like books, handouts, or even mock exams accompanied by online learning, because not all the time the professor has a clear voice during online discussions. Instructors should provide a clear recording of the discussion that comes with visual presentations every discussion to maximize the use of the online class.

References

- Abel Jr, A. (2020). The phenomenon of learning at a distance through emergency remote teaching amidst the pandemic crisis. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), 127-143.
<https://www.asianjde.com/ojs/index.php/AsianJDE/article/view/453/299>

- Adams, R. E., Santo, J. B., & Bukowski, W. M. (2011). The presence of a best friend buffers the effects of negative experiences. *Developmental Psychology*, 47(6), 1786-1791. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0025401>
- Alghamdi, A., Karpinski, A. C., Lepp, A., & Barkley, J. (2020). Online and face-to-face classroom multitasking and academic performance: Moderated mediation with self-efficacy for self-regulated learning and gender. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 102, 214-222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.08.018>
- Allam, S. N. S., Hassan, M. S., Sultan, R., Mohideen, A. F. R., & Kamal, R. M. (2020). Online distance learning readiness during Covid-19 outbreak among undergraduate students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(5), 642-657. https://hrmars.com/papers_submitted/7236/online-distance-learning-readiness-during-covid-19-outbreak-among-undergraduate-students.pdf
- Anderson, M., & Horrigan, J. B. (2016, October 3). *Smartphones help those without broadband get online, but don't necessarily bridge the digital divide*. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2016/10/03/smartphones-help-those-without-broadband-get-online-but-dont-necessarily-bridge-the-digital-divide/>
- Ballado-Tan, J. (2015). Performance in the accountancy licensure examination of the University of Eastern Philippines: A look at curriculum and instruction. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, 11(3), 598-607. <https://ijias.issr-journals.org/abstract.php?article=IJIAS-15-089-04>
- Barrot, J. S., Llenares, I. I., & Del Rosario, L. S. (2021). Students' online learning challenges during the pandemic and how they cope with them: The case of the Philippines. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 7321-7338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10589-x>
- Bisht, R. K., Jasola, S., & Bisht, I. P. (2022). Acceptability and challenges of online higher education in the era of COVID-19: A study of students' perspective. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 11(2), 401-414. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEDS-05-2020-0119>
- Cabatbat, K. P. M. (2022). Bar exam takers amidst the COVID 19 pandemic. *Journal of Public Health*, 44(2), e339-e340. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdab246>
- Chen, B., Seilhamer, R., Bennett, L., & Bauer, S. (2015). Students' mobile learning practices in higher education: A multi-year study. *Educause Review*, 7(3), 225-235. <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2015/6/students-mobile-learning-practices-in-higher-education-a-multiyear-study>
- Dashtestani, R., & Hojatpanah, S. (2022). Digital literacy of EFL students in a junior high school in Iran: voices of teachers, students and Ministry Directors. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 35(4), 635-665. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2020.1744664>
- Doucet, A., Netolicky, D., Timmers, K., & Tuscano, F. J. (2020). *Thinking about pedagogy in an unfolding pandemic (An independent report on approaches to distance learning during covid-19 school closure)*. Work of Education International and UNESCO. https://www.oitcenterfor.org/sites/default/files/file_publicacion/2020_Research_COVID-19.pdf
- Galvez, D. (2020, October 1). *PRC eyes online licensure exams amid COVID-19*. Philippine Daily Inquirer. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1342587/prc-eyes-online-licensure-exams-amid-covid-19>
- Glazier, R. A., Hamann, K., Pollock, P. H., & Wilson, B. M. (2019). Age, gender, and student success: Mixing face-to-face and online courses in political science. *Journal of Political Science Education*, 16(2), 142-157. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15512169.2018.1515636>
- Kapasias, N., Paul, P., Roy, A., Saha, J., Zaveri, A., Mallick, R., & Chouhan, P. (2020). Impact of lockdown on learning status of undergraduate and postgraduate students during COVID-19 pandemic in West Bengal, India. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 116, 105194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105194>
- Knestrick, J. M., Wilkinson, M. R., Pellathy, T. P., Lange-Kessler, J., Katz, R., & Compton, P. (2016). Predictors of retention of students in an online nurse practitioner program. *The Journal for Nurse Practitioners*, 12(9), 635-640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nurpra.2016.06.011>

- Lianza, T. S. (2016). Performance in the CPA Licensure Examinations of Bachelor of Science in Accountancy: Inputs to developmental activities for undergraduate students. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 4(1), 405-414. <https://ijern.com/journal/2016/January-2016/33.pdf>
- Mariani, R., Renzi, A., Di Trani, M., Trabucchi, G., Danskin, K., & Tambelli, R. (2020). The impact of coping strategies and perceived family support on depressive and anxious symptomatology during the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19) lockdown. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11, 587724. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.587724>
- Morgan, J. (2015). The relationship of CPA exam delay after graduation to institutional CPA exam pass rates. *Journal of Finance and Accountancy*, 18(1), 1-11. <https://www.aabri.com/manuscripts/142062.pdf>
- Niemotko, T. J., & Tolan, M. (2020). Online accounting courses: Transition and emerging issues. *The CPA Journal*, 90(5), 11. <https://www.cpapjournal.com/2020/06/24/online-accounting-courses/>
- Nistor, N. (2013). Stability of attitudes and participation in online university courses: Gender and location effects. *Computers & Education*, 68, 284-292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.05.016>
- Oakley, G., & Pegrum, M. (2015). Engaging in networked learning: Innovating at the intersection of technology and pedagogy. *Education Research and Perspectives*, 42, 397-428. <https://search.informit.org/doi/abs/10.3316/ielapa.136242730065555>
- Pattaguan, E. J. P. (2018). Factors that contribute to topping the board licensure examination for certified public accountant. *Pacific Business Review International*, 10(9), 203-214. http://www.pbr.co.in/2018/2018_month/March/23.pdf
- Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. (2021). A literature review on impact of COVID-19 pandemic on teaching and learning. *Higher Education for the Future*, 8(1), 133-141. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347631120983481>
- Richardson, J. T., & Woodley, A. (2003). Another look at the role of age, gender and subject as predictors of academic attainment in higher education. *Studies in Higher Education*, 28(4), 475-493. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0307507032000122305>
- Schroeder, R. (2020). *Wellness and mental health in 2020 online learning*. Inside Higher Ed. <https://www.insidehighered.com/digital-learning/blogs/online-trending-now/wellness-and-mental-health-2020-online-learning>
- Simonds, T. A., & Brock, B. L. (2014). Relationship between age, experience, and student preference for types of learning activities in online courses. *Journal of Educators Online*, 11(1), n1. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1020106.pdf>
- Sison, M. A. (2021, March 5). *Suspended board exams affect thousands of examinees amid the pandemic*. iOrbit News Online. <https://iorbitnews.com/suspended-board-exams-affect-thousands-of-examinees-amid-the-pandemic/>
- Surkhali, B., & Garbuja, C. K. (2020). Virtual learning during COVID-19 pandemic: Pros and cons. *Journal of Lumbini Medical College*, 8(1), 154-155. <https://nepjol.info/index.php/JLMC/article/view/40778>
- Ting, D. S. W., Carin, L., Dzau, V., & Wong, T. Y. (2020). Digital technology and COVID-19. *Nature Medicine*, 26(4), 459-461. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0824-5>
- Wilson, G. (2018). Get connected: Why connectivity and networking remains a challenge for schools. *Education Technology Solutions*, (85), 62-65. <https://search.informit.org/doi/abs/10.3316/informit.094363071268111>
- Wladis, C., Conway, K. M., & Hachey, A. C. (2015). The online STEM classroom- who succeeds? An exploration of the impact of ethnicity, gender, and non-traditional student characteristics in the community college context. *Community College Review*, 43(2), 142-164. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091552115571729>